

Management of Piglet Anaemia

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Abstract

The swine industry played most important role in north east and some other parts of India. The pig is mostly reared for meat production, so it is essential to provide proper care to pigs especially during farrowing and after farrowing. It leads to increase in profits of farm. Among this, management of piglets is very crucial to prevent the piglet anaemia due to low iron content of iron in sow milk. This condition is very fatal for piglet it leads huge losses of pig industry. Hence, it is essential to supplement the iron in form of injection and oral at 4th and 14th day of piglet age to prevent this condition.

Keywords: *Piglet, iron, milk, farrowing*

Introduction

Piglets are pale brown and collect fluid around the throat, chest and internal organs. They may be attacked and affected by various conditions and ailments. Anemia accounts for about 10% of deaths before untreated waste weaning. Pediatric anemia has been a major problem since pig producers began dumping garbage in confinement, denying suckling pigs access to the ground.

Iron is an important component of hemoglobin, a protein that contains about one third of the weight of red blood cells. The red blood hemoglobin has the unique function of transporting oxygen from the lungs to the body's tissues to support cellular metabolism and to transport the resulting carbon metabolism back to the lungs. In the absence of iron deficiency, the piglet cannot absorb a sufficient amount of hemoglobin. Therefore, baby pig anemia is a blood condition in which the oxygen-carrying capacity is greatly reduced, and this condition is usually caused by iron deficiency.

Causes of Iron Anemia Deficiency

Iron deficiency develops rapidly in captive-fed mammals due to (1) low iron retention in the newborn pig, (2) low iron content of colostrum and milk, and (3) depletion of contact iron from the soil (4) the rapid growth rate of the breeding pig. Low iron storage in the newborn pig. Piglets are born with a total of 50mg of iron in their body (liver), most of which are present in the form of hemoglobin in the bloodstream and in the liver. With an iron requirement of about 7mg daily to maintain the level of blood hemoglobin in a normal developing baby, 1 mg is taken or taken with milk and feed. Rapid growth rate of lactating pigs. Compared to other domestic mammals, the baby pig has a greater ability to grow. This rapid growth of growing pig with increasing plasma volume requires high intake of iron to maintain adequate hemoglobin.

Symptoms of Iron Deficiency Anemia

Iron deficiency can range from chronic borderline anemia to severe anemia. Symptoms of chronic anemia are poor growth, loss of appetite, rough hair, wrinkled skin and painful mucous membranes. The most common symptom of severe anemia is difficulty breathing or movement of the diaphragm muscles after exercise, and this is called "thumps." In the worst case scenario, fast-growing pigs may die suddenly due to lack of oxygen. Anemia also reduces the pig's resistance to diseases and respiratory problems, and enteritis can occur more frequently in chronic pigs. Necropsy detection in anemic pigs includes enlargement of the heart and spleen, fluid in the chest and abdomen, and low blood pressure. The mucous membranes can also be seen.

Diagnosis

Piglet anemia is diagnosed by examining unprocessed blood samples and smears during autopsy. By itself, the obvious appearance of pigs can be misleading and should not be relied upon to diagnose anemia.

Treatment

Pigs can get extra iron from injections, oral doses or other means. Once weaned, pigs will usually get enough iron in their diet.

Injecting

Injecting piglets with iron dextran, iron galactan or other iron compounds is a common method of supplementation. The vaccine is usually given before the piglets are 72 hours old. Follow the manufacturer's instructions and apply it to the muscles or under the skin. Clean needles and syringes before use and clean the injection site. Avoid excessive leakage at the injection site by using a suitable hypodermic needle gauge. Pigs are often injured in the injection site and injections in the leg can cause paralysis, increasing the chances of being accidentally bitten by a pig.

1 ml or 100 - 150mg of iron dextran I / M on day 4th and 14th day per pig

Metal compounds can cause muscle spasms in the injection site and these areas do not heal well and are difficult to detect. Error is usually found only by consumers, which lowers the image of a good quality product. Another problem is the occasional development of infections or abscesses in the injection site.

Oral

Natural iron in preparation with iron galactan given to newborn piglets within 18 hours of birth, avoids many complications of iron injections. Pollution, disability and infection are eliminated but repairs are expensive. Pigs should be vaccinated within 18 hours of birth as iron galactan is only absorbed in the intestines at a very young age; similar to the absorption of colostrum. Pigs should receive the full recommended dose and be given a second dose when the first one is renewed. It is not wise to rely on this method when pigs are flooded as digestion may not work properly. Use another method of preparation after 18 hours.

Add a small amount of ferrous sulphate (25mg) and copper sulphate (5mg) to the pork diet or add it to drinking water. Inanimate iron can be given to piglets by mouth to prevent anemia. A moderate amount is absorbed daily through the abdominal wall so repeated administration is required.

Chemicals such as ferrous sulphate are cheaper, but require repeated doses, increased duration and work.

Paint

Paint sows udder with the following combination of Ferrous sulphate 50 gm, copper sulphate 7 gm, Zinc sulfate 3 gm, Sugar 50 gm in one liter of water.

Alternatives

Metal compounds, non-contaminated soil or both can be sprayed in breeding pens, and the provision of feed with iron supplements may be helpful. It has also been reported that piglets can gain iron by licking bare metal in sows and piglets mixed with iron.

Prevention of Iron Deficiency Anemia

There are many ways in which supplemental iron can be given to piglets (1) orally (orally) or (2) by parents (by injection) to meet their iron requirements. These nutrients first appear as plasma iron (transferrin) which is transported from the bone marrow to the production of red cell hemoglobin, to the myoglobin muscle that aids in the conversion of muscle tissue, liver the iron enzyme needed for cellular modification. Injectable muscle-dextran is taken from the muscles by nearby lymph nodes and released into plasma as strong as iron-dextran and can be used for hemoglobin or myoglobin.

Oral

Additional iron can be applied orally (a) by placing the soil in the barn, (b) by swiping the pig's udder with a metal solution, (c) by dipping the pig in metal tablets, pastes or liquids, (d) by inserting fluid, food preparation, pellet or blocks into place incoming, or (e) feeding high levels of iron in pig feed and allowing pigs access to feed and faeces.

The ground

This is an effective way to supply iron when the soil is constantly changing and free of parasite swine eggs. If the creep floor is slightly separated, place the soil on the solid part of the pen concrete. When the creep floor is completely smooth, place the soil on a shallow tray. The disadvantages of this approach are that the workers are involved and have difficulty finding land on which the land is located.

Udder application

If the iron solution is absorbed into the pig's udder daily throughout the milk, this will effectively prevent anemia. However, the work required is far superior to today's pig producers.

Evaluation

A weekly administration of iron pills, pastes or fluid preparations will prevent anemia. What is worse in this way is the work involved in the repetition and the lack of proof that the pig has eaten enough. Placing metal arrangements on the cliff. The number of metal arrangements in the market is designed to be placed in an area that enters the grain pen. These consist of metal solutions with special suppliers, iron salts mixed with peat moss, iron salts mixed with sugary energy sources in the form of food or pellets, and metal blocks designed to be attached to a dividing wall between adjacent bearing pens. Most of these commercial metal arrangements are very effective in preventing anemia if they are properly placed in the entrance area where pigs will feed.

Parental route

The extra iron to prevent anemia can also be controlled by injection. For the metal injections to work effectively, a person must use (a) the right type of metal, (b) the right amount of metal, and (c) the proper metal handling method. Hygiene procedures should be used to prevent the production of abscesses.

Form of metal

The type of iron should be (1) used successfully in hemoglobin production by pigs all the time nursing from a single injection, (2) it is compatible with fluids and tissues and is not toxic in any way to the levels required for treatment, (3) does not cause pain at the injection site, and (4) can be controlled with a small volume of fluid of the right viscosity to allow for the use of a small needle but not causing excessive "running" back. Iron-dextran and iron-dextrin properties, when properly produced, meet all of these processes and are the best alternatives to the market.

Dosing of metal

The right amount of iron you can inject depends on the age at which the pigs will be weaned. If pigs are weaned at 3 weeks of age, 100mg of iron is a sufficient amount for injection. If pigs are weaned over three weeks of age, 150-200mg of iron should be injected. Another way to prevent iron deficiency anemia should be mentioned. It is an oral measurement of newborn pigs with iron dextran. When a newborn pig receives an oral dose of 100-200 mg of iron

from iron-dextran, the iron is effectively absorbed. Recent studies show that this single dose almost acts as an iron injection when the dose occurs within the first six hours of life. However, this method has problems with moderate chance and the possibility of greater iron-dextran dissipation in oral doses compared with injections.

Conclusion

It is concluded that in pig industry the piglet prevents from anaemia during initial phase of life which caused by poor source of iron in sow milk it leads to death of piglet. Hence, it is necessary to prevent the piglet from anemia to maximize the profit to the piggery industry.

References

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